

Quantum Mechanics and Brownian/Stochastic Motion

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As mentioned in previous notes, there exist derivations of the Schrodinger equation in the literature based on stochastic equations and spatial density. In this note, we focus on a particular derivation (1) which makes use of osmotic velocity using an operator which describes a Brownian type motion. The Schrodinger equation follows in (1) from a Newton type equation with d/dt being replaced by an operator which tracks stochastic motion. In particular, the spatial density is set equal to $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ at the last moment, where $W(x,t)$ is a complex function.

We compare the approach of (1) to one in which statistical ideas are applied from the beginning to obtain a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W$. This together with $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$ where $KE_{ave}(x) = \sum_p p^2/2m P(p/x)$ yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation.

We find that the two approaches are consistent, but that in the approach of (1), one does not use the wavefunction until the final steps.

Free Quantum Particle

As in previous notes, we argue that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory, which like classical statistical mechanics, allows a free particle (no potential) to have equal probability to be at any point x . In classical statistical mechanics, the probability would be described by a positive real number. Unlike classical statistical mechanics, where two body collisions determine equilibrium, a bound state quantum particle interacts with a stochastic potential which is only $V(x)$ on average. The idea of a statistical theory is to use "free particles" so one has a momentum distribution at each x . The momentum distribution must be a function of x as average kinetic energy changes from one point to another. If one suggests that d/dx relative probability = momentum probability, then $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution for relative conditional probability i.e. the wavefunction of a free quantum particle. The modulus is 1 allowing for equal probabilities at each x ($P(x)$ not $P(p/x)$). Thus, we argue that initial statistical considerations give rise to the form $\exp(ipx)$ which in turn yields a conditional probability:

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) \text{ where } W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

Using conservation of average energy yields the Schrodinger equation:

$$\sum_p p^2/2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E \quad \text{or} \quad -1/2m (d/dx d/dx W)/W + V = E \quad ((2))$$

In the above, no use of Brownian motion type calculations has been used, but a stochastic potential which is similar to Brownian motion has been utilized. In order to make a connection, one may take the spatial derivative d/dx of ((2)) i.e.

$$-dV/dx = -1/2m (d/dx d/dx d/dx W) / W + 1/m (d/dx \ln W)(d/dx \ln W) \quad ((3))$$

The equation for Brownian motion (2) is:

$$d/dt \text{ (partial) spatial density} = \text{constant } d/x \text{ } d/dx \text{ density} \quad ((4))$$

If one considers force = $-dV/dx = d/dt \langle p \rangle$ then the Brownian motion time derivative appears to be of the form: $d/dt \text{ partial } -\text{constant } d/dx / dx$. It seems this operator acting on $\langle p \rangle$ is part of ((3)) i.e.

$$d/dx \text{ } d/dx \langle p \rangle = d/dx \text{ } d/dx (dW/dx / W) = (d/dx \text{ } d/dx \text{ } d/dx W) / W + \text{other terms} \quad ((5))$$

with the first term on the RHS of ((5)) being the first term on the RHS of ((3)).

Thus, the idea of Brownian motion seems to appear in the spatial derivative of the Schrodinger equation, but in the context of $\langle p \rangle = [\text{Sum over } p \text{ } P(p/x)]$ which is based on $W(x)$ and not spatial density.

Stochastic Operators and the Schrodinger Equation

In (1), a different approach is taken. It is based on stochastic motion which also exists in the above section, but does not begin with the idea of $\exp(ipx)$. Rather, two average velocities are defined:

$$v(x,t) \text{ such that } d/dt \text{ spatial density (partial derivative)} + \text{grad } - (\text{density } v) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

Spatial density is used as the starting point of this theory. Later, at the end of (1), it is suggested that one may mathematically set $\text{density} = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ where $W(x,t)$ is a complex function. Then:

$$v(x,t) = iD (\text{grad}W^*/W^* - \text{grad}W/W) \quad ((7)) \quad \text{where } i \text{ is the complex } i \text{ and } D \text{ a constant}$$

One may immediately see that $v(x,t) = 0$ for a bound state solution $W(x,t) = W(x) \exp(-iEt)$ where $W(x)$ is real. Furthermore, using the free particle solution $\exp(ipx)$ which leads to a density of 1, equation ((6)) is $0=0$.

$$v(x,t) \text{ is associated with an operator: } d/dt \text{ partial} + v.\text{grad} \quad ((8))$$

A second velocity is also defined, namely the diffusion velocity is defined as:

$$u(x,t) = iD \text{ grad density} / \text{density} \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{and associated with the operator } d/dt \text{ partial} + u.\text{grad} + D \text{ grad.grad} \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{In terms of } W(x,t): \quad u(x,t) = D(\text{grad}W^*/W^* + \text{grad}W/W) \quad ((10))$$

For a bound system $u(x,t) = 2D \text{ grad}W/W$. For $\exp(ipx)$ $u(x,t) = 0$ as well.

A main idea of (1) is to describe motion in terms of a kind of Newton's second law (in a slightly simplified form) as:

$$\{d/dt \text{ partial} + 1/m p - \text{grad} + kD \text{ grad.grad}\} p = -\text{grad} V \quad ((11))$$

Here $-\text{grad} V$ is the usual Newton force, $k=-i$ and:

$$P = v+ku = 2iD \text{ grad}(W)/W \quad ((12))$$

For a quantum bound system, however, for which $W(x,t) = \exp(-iEt) W(x)$, $W(x)$ real
 $p = -i2 \text{ grad}(W)/W$

Equations ((11)) and ((12)) are still in the form of densities and so render $0=0$ for $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ (with $-\text{grad}V=0$). $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, however, is the quantum free particle solution and so should be a solution at this point. Later in (1), it is argued that ((11)) is equivalent to a Schrodinger equation, written in terms of $W(x,t)$, which allows for an $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ solution. The approach of the first section immediately yields a Schrodinger type equation for $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ based on the conservation of average energy.

In particular, for $\exp(iPx-iEt)$ $p = 2iD (iP)$ with $P=\text{constant}$ and ((11)) becomes:

$$1/m p.\text{grad}P + kD \text{ grad-grad} (-2DP) = 0 \text{ or } \text{constant} = 1/m (-2DPP) + kD \text{ grad} (-2DP) = -2DPP/m \quad ((13))$$

In other words, in order to solve ((11)) for a free quantum particle with constant momentum P , one would need to introduce the idea of $W=\exp(ipx-iEt)$ at this late stage.

It is at this point, that one tries to convert ((11)) into a Schrodinger equation form using density equals $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$. For a bound state situation one finds:

$$-2i/m D d/dx \ln W \text{ d/dx} (d/dx \ln W) + 2iDD \text{ grad.grad} d/dx \ln W = -\text{grad} V \quad ((14))$$

One may "pull out" grad yielding:

$$-i/m D (d/dx \ln W) (d/dx \ln W) + 2iDD d/dx d/dx \ln W = -V + \text{constant}$$

$$d/dx d/dx \ln W = (d/dx d/dx W) / W - (d/dx \ln W)(d/dx \ln W)$$

The term $-(d/dx \ln W)(d/dx \ln W)$ must ultimately cancel with $-i/m D (d/dx \ln W) (d/dx \ln W)$ in order to yield a Schrodinger equation. In addition, the constant must be related to energy.

Thus, the ideas of the first section based on a momentum probability distribution using $\exp(ipx)$ and conservation of average energy appear to be consistent (and basically equivalent if one uses an appropriate D constant) with the stochastic approach of (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, in section one we have use statistical ideas together with a momentum distribution at each x in the case of a stochastic potential $V(x)$ (on average) to argue that conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$, where $\exp(ipx)$ is the momentum of a free quantum particle. Using average kinetic energy $= \text{Sum over } p \text{ } p^2/2m P(p/x) + V(x) = E$ yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation. The momentum distribution at each x implies stochastic hits to a particle similar to Brownian motion and we have argued that the classical d/dx from Brownian motion appears in quantum mechanics. We have also compared the $P(p/x)$ approach with a stochastic approach developed in (1) which is based on spatial densities, operators describing stochastic diffusion and a kind of Newton's equation. We find that the two approaches lead to essentially the same results, although (1) introduces the idea of spatial density equals $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ at almost the last stage, whereas we introduce it from the beginning.

References

1. De la Pena, L., Cetto, A.M. and Valdes-Hernandez, A. Connecting Two Stochastic Theories that Lead to Quantum Mechanics (May 12, 2020) <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fphy.2020.00162/full>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brownian_motion